

Exploring Tipping Points and Their Impacts
Using Earth System Models

Deliverable D9.2

TipESM Communication and Dissemination Strategy

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1. Introduction

This document presents a communication and dissemination strategy for TipESM, detailing communication objectives, strategies and channels. It presents an overview of primary target audiences and relates them to specific communication and dissemination formats. The document also includes descriptions of tools used in the project to implement and monitor communication and dissemination activities, including the editorial calendar and communication reporting templates.

1.1 About TipESM

TipESM is a Horizon Europe project running from 2024 to 2027. TipESM brings together scientists from a range of disciplines to deliver a step change in our understanding of climate tipping points in the Earth system, including their impact on ecosystems and society, combined with a set of early warning indicators and safe future emission pathways that minimise the risk of exceeding such tipping points.

TipESM assembles the latest Earth System Models (ESMs), including recent improvements to key processes: ice sheets, vegetation and land use, permafrost, marine and terrestrial biogeochemistry. In cooperation with the WCRP/Future-Earth project TIPMIP, TipESM will organise an international collaboration to design and realise a common ESM experiment protocol that will facilitate analysis of the likelihood of occurrence, and potential reversibility, of tipping elements at different levels and duration of global warming. These experiments will be combined with more project-specific ESM experiments, designed to investigate interactions and feedbacks across the Earth system. Based on the TipESM experiments, existing simulations and observations, we will investigate tipping points, their driving processes, potential early warning signals and cascading effects across the climate, ecosystems and society. Including the most important components of the Earth system in our ESMs will also allow TipESM to identify potentially unknown tipping elements, their precursors and impacts.

TipESM brings together expertise from climate science and climate impacts to investigate both the role of gradual climate change for tipping in individual ecosystems and society, and the impact of crossing specific climate tipping points for society, ecosystems, and biodiversity. Project findings will be synthesised into a tipping points risk register. New knowledge and data from TipESM will be communicated regularly to a broad range of research communities, policymakers and the public, contributing to a prepared and resilient society.

1.2 About the TipESM Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The TipESM Communication and Dissemination Strategy sets out the strategic framework for maximising the scientific, environmental and societal impact of TipESM. With a large amount of work carried out in TipESM, the strategy sets out to define and facilitate effective, clear and efficient communication from the project to wider audiences. As such, this communication strategy provides the project consortium with the following information:

1. Target Audiences - who they are expected to communicate with and the key messages linked to these groups.
2. Frequency - when and how often they should be communicating with the groups.
3. How to communicate – which formats they can use to communicate with the different target audiences.

This deliverable outlines and provides detailed information on communication objectives, strategies and channels, definition of target audiences, an editorial calendar for communication and dissemination of project outcomes, and mapping out of relevant events such as conferences and workshops for promoting project results. It also includes a communication reporting template for mapping stakeholders (feeding into task T9.3) and key events. The communication and dissemination activities will be monitored through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which are identified in this strategy.

The strategy works towards the purpose of enhancing European leadership in climate science, promoting the uptake of informed climate adaptation, increasing awareness of the need for a societal transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society, and ensuring the legacy of the project.

The TipESM Communication and Dissemination Strategy is a living document, therefore, it will continue to evolve and will be updated twice during the lifetime of the project. Moreover, a final evaluation of the impact of the dissemination, exploitation and communication will be made at the end of the project in month 46 as part of D10.3 “Final report on Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation”.

2. Communication Objectives

The overall communication objective for TipESM is to **inform, promote, and communicate the activities and results of TipESM to its target audiences for maximising impact and larger uptake**. These activities and future results to be communicated include the knowledge and solutions produced in the project on understanding climate tipping points in the Earth system, their potential impacts on ecosystems and societies, and early warning indicators and safe emission pathways to minimise the risk of exceeding tipping points.

Specifically, TipESM will communicate on:

- Advancing knowledge and solutions in Earth system science, pathways to climate neutrality, climate adaptation and services, social science for climate action, and understanding of climate-ecosystem interactions.
- Contributing to key international assessments such as the IPCC and Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES).
- Strengthening the European Research Area with increased knowledge of the risk of crossing climate tipping points.
- Increasing transparency, robustness and trustworthiness of knowledge on climate and Earth system change, and increasing the practicality of this knowledge for use by policymakers, practitioners, other stakeholders and citizens.

These objectives set the course for the communication activities in TipESM and ensure that effective and meaningful messages are communicated to the most appropriate target audience at the right time.

3. Primary Target Audiences

The table below provides a summary of the primary target audiences with information on the key materials and channels used to reach them. The detailed information is further provided in the sections below the table.

	Written scientific materials	Written non-technical materials	Speaking engagements [Meetings, Seminars, Workshops, Webinars] and policy outreach	Online channels and platforms
Technical Audiences				
Scientific Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peer-reviewed articles Technical project deliverables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Progress reports, grey literature Factsheets, infographics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conference participation Panel discussions Direct engagement Joint seminars and workshops with other projects Roadshow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website Social Media Newsletter [e.g. promoting new publications]
European and International Projects and Initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peer-reviewed articles Project deliverables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Progress reports, grey literature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joint seminars and workshops Conference participation Panel discussions Direct Engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website Social Media Newsletter [e.g. promoting events and communicating their outcomes]
Intergovernmental Organisations and International Assessments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peer-reviewed articles Technical project deliverables 	Infographics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conference participation Panel Discussions Direct Engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website Social Media Newsletter [e.g. promoting events or new publications]

Non-Technical Audiences				
Policymakers, European Parliament and European Commission Services	Summaries of the technical peer-reviewed articles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheets • infographics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ECCA Conference (or similar) • Policy briefings • Side events to COP or similar • Virtual policy roundtables • Knowledge4policy events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social Media • Newsletter [e.g. sharing factsheets, infographics] EEA Climate- ADAPT platform
General Audiences				
General public and wider society	Information published in peer-reviewed articles will be converted in easy-to-understand texts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factsheets, • infographics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National/European science fairs and outreach events • Public lectures and presentations • Panel discussions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social Media • Newsletter [e.g. sharing project introductions or thematic campaigns]

Table 1. Summary of target audiences and related communication formats.

3.1 Technical Audiences - Scientific Community

To advance knowledge in Earth system science, social science for climate action, and understanding of climate-ecosystem interactions, TipESM will engage with an audience of technical users interested in the project's scientific outcomes. These groups broadly cover specific scientific aspects addressed across TipESM's Science Themes indicated in the Description of the Action (DoA):

- Simulating tipping points in the Earth system with the latest generation of Earth System Models.
- New knowledge on climate tipping points and their driving processes.
- Early warning indicators and the risk for cascades of tipping points in the climate and ecosystems.
- Identifying climate change-driven tipping points in ecosystems and society.
- New knowledge on the impacts of climate-tipping events on ecosystems and society.
- Future tipping point risks and safe mitigation emission pathways.

These target audiences are interested both in the advancement of knowledge on the risks of exceeding key climate tipping points and also in their impacts on ecosystems and wider society.

The communication and dissemination to the technical audiences has several key objectives:

- To encourage collaboration and stakeholder engagement with the project where necessary.
- To exchange critical information relevant to the project's development and achieving reliable results.
- To advance the knowledge about climate tipping points and their impacts among the technical audiences.
- To ensure and validate that the final results are as relevant as possible to the targeted stakeholders.

3.1.1 Scientific Community

Who are they?

The scientific community includes the specialist and wider scientific community. The specialist scientific community is made up of scientists working across the disciplines directly addressed in the work of TipESM. This involves, among others: Earth system and impact modelling researchers, scientists within climate, physics, biogeochemistry, biology, social science, health, Tipping Points, and abrupt ecosystem change, as well as teams developing future emission and mitigation pathways. Those within the wider scientific

community, include scientists who do not directly work across the disciplines addressed by TipESM, but may still harbour an interest in the results of the project. These groups might include urban planners, engineers, political scientists, economists and others.

Language register

Technical. It can be expected that scientists who specialise in the field of study in TipESM are familiar with technical terms, the latest theories and modelling techniques and the various institutions, partners and initiatives associated with TipESM. For those in the wider scientific community, it is likely that they have an interest in and experience with climate science on some level. Therefore, it can be assumed that more commonly used technical terms are known to this group.

Objective

Communication with the scientific community sets out to inform about the work and results from TipESM, and to exchange knowledge and initiate collaboration with other researchers in the field. Integration of knowledge and collaboration with specialists will help maximise the impact and exploitation of project outcomes as well as further raise awareness of the work being conducted.

Potential contents

- Project progress and results (also mid-term) for the specific scientific specialist communities.
- Opportunities for collaboration and idea development.

Primary tools

- Direct contact with specific networks (such as TIPMIP, the Tipping Point International Intercomparison Project) or via Advisory Board (e.g. representatives of IPBES, Copernicus Climate Change Service, ESA CCI etc.).
- Peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals.
- Technical project deliverables.
- Conference participation.
- Panel discussions at relevant events.
- Direct engagement at meetings, seminars, workshops, webinars.
- Social Media.
- Roadshow.

- Factsheets, infographics.
- Progress reports, grey literature.
- Website: Home, About, Outreach.

3.1.2 European and International Initiatives and Projects

Who are they?

The European and international initiatives and projects targeted for engagement by TipESM are those with obvious synergies and mutual collaboration benefits. Relevant projects include ClimTip, OptimESM, ESM2025, TIPMIP, COMFORT, TiPPACS, TiPES, CMIP, European Environment Agency (EEA), and the ESA Climate Change Initiative.

Language register

Technical. It can be expected that projects and initiatives implemented in this field are familiar with technical terms, the latest theories and modelling techniques, and the broader scientific and project community.

Objective

The key objective for communicating with European and international initiatives and projects is to explore synergies and potential for their exploitation. Through close communication and exchange, the initiatives and projects can develop a shared understanding of the respective projects and project outcomes; develop an understanding of how the respective projects relate to one another and how the results can influence other projects; ensure synchronisation of activities for addressing open science questions; and demonstrate value added through collaborative working.

Potential contents

- Project description, progress, and results.
- Opportunities for collaboration and idea development.
- Demonstration of tools for greater understanding of tipping points risks and potential shocks to the climate, ecosystems and society.
- Policy relevance of the project and its results.

Primary tools

- Joint workshops and seminars.
- Conference participation.
- Panel discussions at relevant events.
- Peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals.
- Direct engagement via online and face-to-face meetings.
- Deliverables, progress reports, grey literature.
- Website: Home, About, Partners & Collaborators, Outreach, Events.

3.1.3 Intergovernmental Organisations and International Assessments

Who are they?

In expanding the knowledge on climate tipping points and their potential ecosystem and societal impacts, TipESM will contribute to the work of various intergovernmental organisations and climate assessments, such as: International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), World Climate Research Programme (WCRP), Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), and World Meteorological Organisation (WMO). Representatives of these organisations are advisors to TipESM. Outputs of TipESM will address key knowledge gaps and provide increased confidence in assessments of climate tipping points.

Language register

Technical. It can be expected that the intergovernmental organisations and assessments working in this field are familiar with technical terms, the latest theories, and the broader scientific community. It is recommended that the communication matches and builds on the communication from the targeted organisations and assessments (e.g. referencing IPCC or IPBES assessments).

Objective

The aim of engagement with intergovernmental organisations and assessments is to contribute to their work by providing new knowledge and delivering capabilities to assess the risk of exceeding key climate tipping points and the associated ecological and societal impacts. The goal is to inform and engage these organisations with the results of TipESM, consequently helping shape future priorities in Earth system

modelling, scenario development, climate services, climate impact assessment and science-policy interaction.

Potential contents

- Project progress and results as they are rolled out.
- Climate assessment relevance of the project and its results.
- Methodologies and tangible scientific outcomes that can be applied to support climate assessments.

Primary tools

- Direct engagement via online and face-to-face meetings, participation in the TipESM project meetings and activities.
- Peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals.
- Technical project deliverables.
- Conference participation.
- Panel discussions.
- Website: Home, Outreach.

3.2 Non-Technical Audiences

Non-technical audiences are those interested in how the advancements in tipping points analysis and understanding their associated ecological and societal impacts will translate into tangible benefits for wider society, rather than in the scientific core aspects of TipESM.

3.2.1 Policymakers, European Parliament and European Commission Services

Who are they?

Policymakers at European level and the European Commission Services are the decision-makers who have the power and responsibility to set policy based on the information they receive. New knowledge and information developed as a result of TipESM will be relevant to decision-makers at all levels of governance from local to EU and global levels. A key aim of TipESM is to maintain a regular two-way dialogue with European policymakers to ensure the research is both informed by and supports policy needs.

With the European Commission Services, the activities under Horizon Europe Clusters: CL5 (Climate, Energy, Mobility), CL4 (Digital, Industry, Space) and CL6 (Food, Natural Resources, Agriculture, Environment) are relevant to TipESM. Additionally, the Horizon Europe Missions including “Adaptation to Climate Change”, “Climate Neutral and Smart Cities” and “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” will be targeted as TipESM outputs can complement activities under these missions’ mandate. Within the European Commission services, the following Directorate Generals have been identified as critical: DG RTD, DG Connect, DG ENV, and DG MARE.

Language register

Technical, but non-specialist. Documentation must use language relevant across a broad range of disciplines and therefore, where possible avoid very specific technical terms.

Objective

To ensure project outputs can be easily understood and integrated and to provide evidence for policy and decision-making on mitigation pathways, safe operating spaces for humanity and ecosystems and adaptation strategies.

Specifically at the EU level, the objective is to support EU Adaptation and Mitigation Services and maximise the impact of the Horizon Europe missions.

Potential contents

- Project progress and results.
- Policy relevance of the project and its results.
- Tangible scientific results that can be used as a basis for evidence-based decision-making and policymaking.

Primary tools

- Policy briefings and briefs.
- Factsheets, infographics.
- European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA) or similar.
- Participation in side events to major venues such as the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030), COP events, or similar.
- Virtual policy roundtables.

- Knowledge4Policy events organised by the EC services and agencies.
- European Environmental Agency's Climate-ADAPT platform.
- Website: Home, About, Outreach, Events.

3.3 General Audiences

To increase the transparency, trustworthiness, and practical usability of the knowledge base on climate change and tipping points, TipESM will engage with general audiences. While they are not the primary target group for the project's communication and dissemination activities, there is significant value to be gained from engaging with general audiences. Among others, it will help ensure widespread coverage of project results, securing their uptake in various scientific fields and changing the citizens' perception of climate change and its impacts on their daily life.

The communication and dissemination to the general audiences has several key objectives:

- To increase awareness about climate change, risks of exceeding tipping points and impacts of such events, and the need for immediate climate action and adaptation
- To stimulate engagement with and appreciation for climate science and the value of work of scientists and researchers more broadly

3.3.1 The general public and wider society

Who are they?

The general public and wider society represent individuals and organisations that are interested in the work and results of TipESM, but are connected to the project and climate science only peripherally. This group includes private citizens, especially youth action groups, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), students, civil society, and journalists with interest in climate and the environment.

Language register

Non-technical. The general public and wider society may have limited knowledge of climate issues and climate science beyond what is commonly shared in the media. Therefore, technical language should be avoided, and any terms specific to climate science should be briefly explained in simple terms. For some members of this audience such as relevant NGOs and youth action groups who may be competent across

fields related to policy and the impacts of climate change, communication and dissemination will require non-technical-specialist language.

Furthermore, this audience is unlikely to have prior knowledge of administrative terms related to European funded projects, such as the Horizon Europe framework. If such terms cannot be avoided, it is recommended to include a basic explanation.

Objective

Key objectives include increasing awareness of climate and Earth system change, why adaptation strategies are necessary to prepare for future extreme weather and climate, pathways to climate neutrality, as well as increasing the useability of knowledge for climate action.

Potential contents

- Project description (motivation, action, impact).
- Project results and implications for society (translated into non-technical language through appropriate communication formats).

Primary tools

- Social Media.
- Website.
- Factsheets, infographics.
- Roadshows at national/European science fairs and science outreach events.
- Public lectures and presentations.
- Panel discussions at relevant events involving the general public (Open Days, Night of Science, etc.) organised by the partners' institutes.

4. Communication Formats

4.1 Written Scientific Materials

Written scientific communication, including peer-reviewed articles and technical deliverables, will be an important format to reach the technical audiences of TipESM. This communication format will be used to disseminate new knowledge on tipping points and their impacts generated in TipESM, using technical language and following the writing guidelines of specific journals.

4.1.1 Peer-Reviewed Articles

It is expected that the project will result in a number of publications in scientific, peer-reviewed journals, especially during its final year. Peer-reviewed articles are to be used as a tool for technical knowledge dissemination and as a method for inviting specialist feedback on research conducted by the TipESM consortium. The goal of scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals is to ensure broad advancement of tipping points research and continued scientific debate also beyond the project duration.

TipESM scientists will ensure that electronic copies of peer-reviewed scientific publications become freely available to anyone as soon as possible (no embargo time) and in open access.

- A comprehensive list of the journals is provided by the Directory of Open Access Journals: <http://www.doaj.org>
- The publisher policies for the pathways to open access for each journal can be consulted here: <http://www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/index.php>

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
Infrequently, depending on the research progress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialist scientific community • European and international projects and initiatives • Intergovernmental organisations and international assessments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of published articles • Feedback on articles, also in terms of sharing and citing (see in section 8 of this document)

4.1.2 Technical project deliverables

TipESM will produce a number of technical deliverables showcasing project progress and final results. The deliverables will serve as an important communication format for knowledge dissemination. They will be written in a technical language and presented as reports, data sets, or online interactive tools (in the case of Deliverable 7.3.).

Public deliverables will be made available on the TipESM Zenodo Community: [TipESM \(zenodo.org\)](https://zenodo.org/communities/tipesm).

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
Based on the project schedule	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specialist scientific community European and international projects and initiatives Intergovernmental organisations and international assessments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of views on Zenodo Number of downloads on Zenodo Sharing and reposting of materials Citations of materials in official reports

4.2 Written Non-technical Materials

These resources intend to disseminate research findings to target audiences using accessible language and visuals. These materials highlight potential impacts on society, ecosystems and biodiversity. These resources can be used both online and in-person as printed materials brought to events such as conferences and policy briefings.

4.2.1 Progress reports, grey literature

As opposed to scientific writing, grey literature includes information that is produced and disseminated outside of traditional publishing channels (and thus may not be represented in indexing databases). Any progress reports, working papers, conference proceedings, or white papers will likely be considered grey literature. It is characterised by the use of more accessible language and visuals, thus targeting a broader audience than just the scientific community.

In TipESM, this communication format will include:

- Publishable summaries made available for every deliverable, milestone and for the official periodic reports.

- Articles and short reports with materials and research produced by organisations outside of the traditional commercial or academic publishing.

Progress reports and grey literature developed in TipESM will be made available on the TipESM Zenodo Community: [TipESM \(zenodo.org\)](https://zenodo.org/communities/tipesm).

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
Based on the project schedule	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialist scientific community • European and international projects and initiatives • Intergovernmental organisations and international assessments • General public and wider society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of views on Zenodo • Number of downloads on Zenodo • Sharing and reposting of materials • Citations of materials in official reports

4.2.2 Factsheets

Factsheets are used to highlight the main features of the project. They are intended to be one-pagers where a wide range of audiences can easily access and understand the project activities, partnership, objectives, and expected impacts. Therefore, the language on factsheets should be understandable for most audiences. Factsheets can be distributed to those outside of the project so that they can grasp a quick understanding and overview of the project. Moreover, factsheets can also be printed and distributed at events to inform about the project, activities and any results.

The first [factsheet for TipESM has been published on the Zenodo Community](#). This factsheet summarises and showcases the project’s background and motivation, the action to be implemented, expected impacts, partners and collaborators, conceptual diagram of how the project works, and a general project snapshot.

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
Dependent on the publishing of project/research results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific community • Policymakers, European Parliament and European Commission Services • General public and wider society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of views on Zenodo • Number of downloads on Zenodo • Sharing and reposting of materials

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citations of materials in official reports
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4.2.3 Infographics

Infographics are visual tools to portray and summarise data, statistics, facts, information and reports effectively. They are particularly useful in reaching non-specialist audiences. Infographics can be embedded in documents (such as PowerPoint presentations or public reports) and can also be incorporated into social media content which reaches a wider non-specialist audience.

Online resources will be made available on the TipESM Zenodo Community: [TipESM \(zenodo.org\)](https://zenodo.org).

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
Dependent on the publishing of project/research results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific community • Policymakers, European Parliament and European Commission Services • General public and wider society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of views on Zenodo • Number of downloads on Zenodo • Sharing and reposting of materials • Citations of materials in official reports

4.3 Speaking engagements

A speaking engagement is an opportunity to speak in front of an audience on a specific topic. In case of TipESM, typical speaking engagements will include presentations at various conferences, participation in panel discussions, workshops, seminars, and webinars, presentations at science fairs and science festivals, various roadshow events, and direct online or face-to-face engagement. Speaking engagements provide a chance to engage in a two-way communication with target audiences, focused on both disseminating information but also receiving questions and feedback. Speaking engagements will be an important and frequently used communication format for TipESM to engage with diverse technical, non-technical, and general audiences. Language, communication materials (presentations, hand-outs) and tone will be adjusted to target specific audiences depending on the event.

4.3.1 Conference participation

TipESM’s project and its results will be presented by scientists and project partners at various conferences. In each case communication will be tailored according to the target audience of the conference. Through conference participation, TipESM will maximise the interaction and networking possibilities with the scientific community and other Horizon projects. Where possible, we will try to implement specific TipESM sessions (or sessions specific to TipESM research areas) within established scientific conferences.

Presentations made at conferences will be made available on TipESM Zenodo Community: [TipESM \(zenodo.org\)](https://zenodo.org)

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
Regularly but dependent on conference schedules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific community European and international projects and initiatives Intergovernmental organisations and international assessments Policymakers, European Parliament and European Commission Services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of conferences participated in/invited to also as keynote speaker Participant feedback during Q&A

4.3.2 Panel discussions, workshops, seminars and webinars

Panel discussions, workshops and seminars are an effective method of engaging in dialogue with targeted audiences. They present an opportunity to communicate and discuss the broader implications of TipESM results and how they can lead to industry- or policy developments. As an interactive form of communication, panel discussions, workshops and seminars can be used both to disseminate project results to end users but also to receive their feedback where needed.

Webinars are a combination of a speaking engagement and online channel of communication, presenting great benefits in terms of logistics and use of resources. They do not require the same commitment from attendees (in terms of e.g. travel and time commitments), so higher participation can be expected - also from “less-interested” audiences.

TipESM will also continue the format of the climate coffees started under Blue-Action and picked up by the [OCEAN:ICE project](#) and the European Climate Research Alliance.

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
In connection with the publishing of project/research results and events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All target audiences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of speaking engagements, also as keynote speaker Number of participants (registration/attendance) Participant feedback during Q&A

4.3.3 Science fairs and outreach events

Participation in science fairs and science outreach events will be a way for TipESM to engage with the general public and wider society, particularly students, NGOs, and youth action groups. The objective of presenting at science fairs and outreach events is to increase the public awareness of climate and Earth system change, highlight the importance of adaptation to prepare for future extreme weather and climate, and increase the useability of knowledge for climate action.

Participating in science fairs and science festivals to promote TipESM and its results will be conducted as part of the Roadshow (see below).

Examples of science fairs and outreach events relevant to TipESM include but are not limited to: Climateurope2 Festival, Bloom Festival or Pint of Science events.

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
In connection with existing science fairs and science festivals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General public and wider society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of science fairs and outreach events Participants (feedback and interactions, attendance/registration) For the presented materials: number of views and download

4.3.4 Roadshow

The TipESM roadshow is a series of events (online and in-person) and communications generating buzz around the project results. The events will be organised in connection with larger conferences, events, and public science festivals to ensure maximum visibility. The roadshow presents a good opportunity to:

- Inform about and raise awareness of TipESM, tipping points research and its impacts.
- Discuss the relevance of project results for various stakeholders.
- Conduct question-and-answer sessions.

The information presented at the roadshow events will be translated to online versions and used as communication material on TipESM website, newsletter and social media.

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
In connection with existing conferences, events and science festivals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific community • European and international projects and initiatives • General public and wider society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For the presented materials: number of views and download • Participants (feedback and interactions, attendance/registration) • Number of TipESM speakers in these activities

4.3.5 Direct engagement

Direct engagement refers to the process of contacting individual stakeholders directly in order to make them aware of the work and process TipESM is making. Direct contact to relevant stakeholders will be established through the extensive network of TipESM project partners, engagement in various networks and initiatives, and the Advisory Board.

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
On an ad-hoc basis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific community • European and international projects and initiatives • Intergovernmental organisations and assessments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of interactions (meetings etc) • Number of stakeholders reached • For the presented materials: number of views and download • Participants (feedback and interactions, attendance/registration)

4.4 Policy outreach

The results of TipESM as they are rolled out will provide valuable information for evidence-based policymaking. In order to bridge the science-policy gap, TipESM will communicate with policymakers through a series of outreach activities, including policy briefings and written policy briefs, as well as dissemination of project results through policy engagement events (e.g. related to Knowledge4Policy platform or the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030)).

4.4.1 Policy Briefings

TipESM will hold two policy briefings throughout the lifetime of the project. Policy briefings refer to meetings with European and national representatives/policymakers. The policy briefings are to be used to inform decision makers about topics related to the project such as tipping points, risks, early warning indicators, societal and ecosystem impacts and safe future mitigation pathways. They are targeted at policymakers (European Commission services and agencies, European Parliament) to ensure that project outputs can be easily understood and integrated.

Policy briefs refer to the reports which will be created in conjunction with the policy briefing meetings. These reports and any other materials created will be made available on the TipESM Zenodo Community: [TipESM \(zenodo.org\)](https://zenodo.org/communities/tipesm/).

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
First policy briefing: M29 or M30 Second policy briefing: M44 or M45	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers, European Parliament (EP) and European Commission Services (EC) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to other project's policy briefs as experts /contribution to policy briefs of other projects • Number of TipESM speakers in these activities • Number of attendees at policy briefings (registration and attendance) • Citations of the material in future policy reports drafted by EP/EC

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For the presented materials: number of views and downloads
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4.4.2 Policy Engagement Activities

In connection with the policy briefings to be held, TipESM will also partake in ad hoc dissemination and policy engagement activities. These activities complement the policy briefings and work towards conveying the role climate services can play in informing and supporting policies and initiatives.

Events for policy engagement include side events to major events such as COP or United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030), town halls, and EU Knowledge4Policy events. Activities under this measure work in connection with Task 9.3 Making TipESM Science Actionable and will involve the Stakeholder Reference Group and the Advisory group members.

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
Dependent on the publishing of project/research results and events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers, European Parliament (EP) and European Commission Services (EC) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to other project’s policy briefs as experts /contribution to policy briefs of other projects • Number of TipESM speakers in these activities • Number of attendees at policy briefings (registration and attendance) • Citations of the material in future policy reports drafted by EP/EC • Presentations: Number of views on Zenodo • Presentation: Number of downloads on Zenodo

4.5 Online channels

Online communication offers a convenient, quick and cost-effective way to connect with diverse audiences worldwide. Here we define online communication channels that rely primarily on written or graphical communication, such as project website, newsletter, and social media. Conferences, presentations, webinars, or meetings that take place online are categorised as “Speaking engagements”.

In TipESM, online communication channels will be frequently used to share different content and reach all target audiences. Depending on the target audience, the content can vary from information about project progress and results to coordinated campaigns that raise awareness about tipping points and their impacts. By reaching diverse audiences at a large scale through online communication channels, we aim to amplify the impact of TipESM.

4.5.1 Project Website

The project website is the central reference point for the project where visitors can find user-friendly information. The website contains the following sections and will be updated and evolve throughout the lifetime of the project with new content:

- **Home page** showcasing the latest news
- **About page** describing what TipESM sets out to do and the expected impacts to be generated
- **Partners & Collaborators page** outlining the TipESM consortium, external collaborators, and connected initiatives and EU-funded projects
- **Outreach page** where visitors can access information about the project on the TipESM Zenodo Community, and resource materials such as the video series TipESM Explained
- **Events page** listing the upcoming and past events connected with TipESM
- **Contact page** with the emails of the Project Coordinator and Project Office at DMI

Website URL: <https://www.tipesm.eu/>

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
Regularly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All target audiences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visits per month (unique visitors and recurring visitors)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time spent on the webpages
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4.5.2 Newsletter via LinkedIn

A newsletter will be set up to raise awareness and to communicate project updates, news, and progress in TipESM. The newsletter is set out to be quarterly based via the LinkedIn page, as a news feature. Features in the newsletter will inform readers on the following content:

- Project achievements, publications, events, and media
- Past or present events associated with TipESM
- Features from the project researchers (such as Researcher in the Spotlight, or pieces from the researchers themselves)

The newsletter will be hosted on the TipESM LinkedIn page through the newsletter feature. It will be also shared in PDF with a link to Zenodo to reach the audiences who are not on LinkedIn.

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
Quarterly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All target audiences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter subscribers • Number of views/downloads (in Zenodo and LinkedIn)

4.5.3 Social Media

Social media represents a wide reaching and cost effective method of engaging large audiences. It allows us to connect with diverse stakeholders from the start and target them with relevant messages. Different campaigns will be planned and launched to reach specific audiences. Examples of social media content include but are not limited to:

- Posts promoting new scientific publications, targeted to the scientific community.
- Information about and promotion of upcoming events, targeted to the general public and wider society.
- Campaigns highlighting particular scientific results, or explaining key concepts related to tipping points and their impacts, targeted the general public and wider society.

LinkedIn and YouTube are identified as social media platforms particularly relevant to TipESM, although other platforms such as X (formerly Twitter) and others may be relevant for the activities of some partners.

Frequency	Target Audiences	Key Performance Indicators
Regularly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All target audiences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of followers Engagement with the posts (liking, sharing, commenting)

5. Editorial Calendar

An editorial calendar for communication and dissemination of project outcomes, and mapping out of relevant events such as conferences and workshops for promoting project results has been created for the first year of the project and will be updated throughout the lifetime of TipESM. The editorial calendar is a living tool, which utilises inputs from the TipESM Activity Tracker to map relevant events.

The editorial calendar outlines the communication tools to be used (ex: project website, factsheets, newsletter, YouTube), publish date, author, content, topic/title, source of content and status of the editorial. For the first year of TipESM, editorial content focuses on project description, progress, and results as well as speaking engagements such as conferences and panel discussion where the project has been promoted/involved in.

6. Communication Reporting Template

A TipESM communication reporting template for mapping stakeholders (feeding into T9.3) and key events has been developed via online tools to collect this information. In relation to stakeholder mapping, a Miro board has been co-created with the TipESM consortium to map out key organisations and stakeholder groups.

A template for communication reporting for key events (pre- and post-event) has been set up online to gather information from the TipESM partners. This template will be distributed to partners on a monthly basis for both scoping upcoming key events as well as following up attended events. The template can be accessed here: [TipESM Activity Tracker](#).

Using the template, the following information is collected:

- Name of the activity (conference, education and training event, meeting, etc.)
- Short description of the activity
- Date of the activity
- Location
- TipESM project partners involved
- WPs relevant to the activity
- Target audience
- Number of participants
- Relevant files: presentations, posters, publications (to be published on Zenodo)

A screenshot of a web form titled "TipESM Activity Tracker". The form is enclosed in a light blue border and contains the following sections:

- Header:** The TipESM logo and title.
- Introduction:** A paragraph asking users to report activities (events, workshops, publications, etc.) and explaining that the information will be used to report to the European Commission and on TipESM channels.
- Account:** A "Switch account" link and a small icon.
- Privacy:** A note stating that the user's name, email, and photo associated with their Google account will be recorded upon submission.
- Legend:** A red asterisk indicating required questions.
- Email:** A text input field labeled "Email *" with the placeholder "Your email".
- Activity Name:** A dropdown menu labeled "Name of the communication/dissemination activity *" with the placeholder "Choose".
- Description:** A text area labeled "Tell us about the activity. *" with two prompts: "If the activity is upcoming: what will your contributions be?" and "If the activity has taken place: what are the key takeaways? What should we tell the TipESM Community about the activity? What did you present?". Below the text area is a "Your answer" label and a text input field.
- Date:** A date picker labeled "Date of the activity" with the placeholder "mm/dd/yyyy" and a calendar icon.
- Location:** A text area labeled "Location" with the prompt "Where does/did the activity take place?". Below the text area is a "Your answer" label and a text input field.

Figure 1. TipESM Activity Tracker.

7. Accessibility and inclusivity of communication and dissemination materials

All published materials will be produced in compliance with the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) for ensuring maximum accessibility to people with disabilities.

The full overview of the WCAG standards and guidelines can be found on the website here:

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/wcag/>

8. Monitoring the uptake of peer-reviewed publications

The more a publication is shared, downloaded, read and cited, the stronger is its usefulness, impact and value.

8.1 Tools for monitoring impact of a publication

A number of tools are available to monitor the impact of a publication, for instance:

- Dimensions
- ResearchGate Research Interest
- Publisher's stats on cumulative views and downloads (whenever available)
- Google scholar Index: citations
- ResearchGate: Citations, Downloads and Reads
- Altmetric Attention score: Online Attention

In TipESM, we have chosen a combination of the following:

- Dimensions <https://app.dimensions.ai/discover/publication>
- ResearchGate Research Interest <https://www.researchgate.net/search>
- Altmetric Attention score: Online attention (via Dimensions)

Their combination allows us to get the best picture possible on the impact of the publications.

Tools / Functionalities	Publisher's Stats	Google scholar Index	Altmetric Attention score	Dimensions' Badge	ResearchGate	ResearchGate Research Interest
Citations		Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Reads	Yes				Yes	Yes
Downloads	Yes				Yes	Yes
Geo-Location users	Yes		Yes	Via Altmetric Attention Score		
Sharing online			Yes	Via Altmetric Attention Score		
Interdisciplinarity				Yes		
Link to UN SDGs				Yes		
Recommendations						Yes

Table 2: Monitoring impact of publications.

Dimensions

Dimension citations are the total number of times a publication has been cited. Dimensions count citations from the reference list in all publications that have been indexed by Dimensions. Dimensions allows us to monitor by whom the research underlying the publication has been funded, the interdisciplinarity of the research and also the impact of the specific publication contents to the achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

ResearchGate Research Interest

ResearchGate focuses on these interactions to reflect the lifecycle of a scientist's increasing interest in a piece of research: reads, recommendations, citations. When researchers read, recommend or cite a research item, its ResearchGate Interest goes up. First, a researcher accesses a research item. If it sounds of interest, they may read the full-text (if it is available). If they like what they read, they might recommend it. If the work is really relevant, they might cite it in their own research. The research interest has been created based on ResearchGate data and the feedback from scientists.

Altmetric

Altmetric is a high-level measure of the quality and quantity of online attention that a publication has received. The scoring algorithm takes various factors into account, such as the relative reach of the

different sources of attention. Altmetric collects relevant mentions from social media sites, newspapers, policy documents, blogs, Wikipedia, and many other sources.

8.2 Tools for monitoring ranking of the journals

In TipESM we will monitor the ranking of the journals where we publish by using CiteScore.

We will screen the 10% top journals per subject area and cross-check how many publications of TipESM in the each reporting period are published in the top 10% highest ranking journals per subject areas.

The more our authors publish on CiteScore high ranking journals, the stronger the reach, the impact and the value of their article. This is an excellent indicator that the TipESM community has been able to create high quality new knowledge of the scientific impact and the quality of the results.